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CHARACTERISTICS OF THE MICROBIOCENOSIS OF THE ORAL CAVITY OF ONCOLOGICAL PATIENTS DURING PROSTHETICS WITH VARIOUS STRUCTURAL MATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

This article presents a literature review of the latest collected data concerning the study of the characteristics of the microbiocenosis of the oral cavity in patients with oncological diseases of the maxillofacial region. The study of the microbial flora of the oral cavity in oncological diseases of the maxillofacial area is promising in this aspect. It is important to study the mechanisms of adhesion and colonization of individual representatives of the microbial flora of the oral cavity to various types of materials for prosthetics.

Keywords: microbiocenosis, jaw tumors, acrylic prosthesis, adhesion.

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ХАРАКТЕРИСТИКА МИКРОБИОЦЕНОЗА ПОЛОСТИ РТА ОНКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ БОЛЬНЫХ ПРИ ПРОТЕЗИРОВАНИИ РАЗЛИЧНЫМИ КОНСТРУКЦИОННЫМИ МАТЕРИАЛАМИ

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлен литературный обзор последних собранных данных, касающихся исследования особенностей микробиоценоза полости рта у больных с онкологическими заболеваниями челюстно-лицевой области. Изучение микробной флоры полости рта при онкологических заболеваниях ЧЛЮ является перспективным в рассматриваемом аспекте. Важным представляется изучение механизмов адгезии и колонизации отдельных представителей микробной флоры полости рта к различным видам материалов для протезирования.

Ключевые слова: микробиоценоз, опухоли челюстей, акриловый протез, адгезия.

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Jarrohlik stomatologiyasi kafedrasini assistenti**TURLI TUZILMA MATERIALLAR BILAN PROTEZLASH DAVRIDA ONKOLOGIK BEMORLARNING OG'IZ BOSH'LIGI MIKROBIOTSENOZINING XUSUSIYATLARI****ANNOTATSIYA**

Ushbu maqolada yuz-jag'i qismining onkologik kasalliklari bo'lgan bemorlarda og'iz bo'shlig'i mikrobiotsenozining xususiyatlarini o'rganish bo'yicha to'plangan so'nggi ma'lumotlarning adabiyot sharhi keltirilgan. Bu jihatda yuz-jag'i qismining onkologik kasalliklarida og'iz bo'shlig'ining mikrob florasini o'rganish istiqbolli hisoblanadi. Og'iz bo'shlig'i mikrobial florasining alohida vakillarining protezlash uchun har xil turdagi materiallarga yopishish va kolonizatsiya mexanizmlarini o'rganish muhimdir.

Kalit so'zlar: mikrobiotsenoz, jag' o'smalari, akril protezlar, yopishqoqlik.

Introduction. Despite continuous improvement in the design of dental prostheses (treatment devices) and the use of new constructional materials after the application of removable prostheses. Especially in the early postoperative period, complications often develop due to the accumulation of resident oral microflora of varying degrees of virulence, leads to inflammation of the mucosa of the prosthetic bed and prosthetic stomatitis. [7] The severity of these complications determines the medical, biological and social significance of this pathology of the maxillofacial system. The individual intolerance of the base material of the removable therapeutic appliance and oral microbiocenosis that contribute to the mobilization of the adaptation-compensatory mechanisms supporting the homeostasis of the organism have a leading role in choosing the construction material for the base of the prosthesis-obturator [6].

Research methods and materials. Oral microflora is one of the most informative indicators of the state of the body as a whole and the dental system in particular. The peculiarity of this ecosystem, according to I.I. Oleynik, is that it is under the constant double influence, both from the body and the multifactorial influence of the environment. The formation of human oral microbiocenosis occurs gradually in its development, the species and quantitative composition of which remain relatively unchanged during life. The qualitative composition of microbes that make up the oral microbiocenosis depends on 3 main factors: adhesion (ability to adhere), growth and reproduction.

Many microbes pass through the oral cavity, but only those that can attach and stay in the oral cavity have the opportunity to become permanent inhabitants - residents. According to modern concepts, the "normal" or resident oral mucosal microflora is represented mainly by facultative-anaerobic and obligate-anaerobic bacteria [14].

The resident microflora plays a crucial role in some functions, the most important of which are metabolic, synthetic and detoxification, activity, participation in digestive processes, formation of natural human immunity, and, finally, providing colonization resistance/ The oral cavity is an open ecosystem and one of the main routes of penetration of microorganisms from the external environment. Along with this, the species composition of the oral microflora is characterized by a known constancy and is represented by aerobic and anaerobic microorganisms. [2,3]

The leading position in the composition of the typical and permanent representatives of the aerobic flora of the oral cavity is occupied by streptococci, which account for 30 to 60% of the bacterial flora of the oral cavity. The prominent representatives are *S. salivarius*, *S. mitis*, *S. mutans*, *S. sanguis*. [1]

Among anaerobic forms of microorganisms in the oral cavity there are representatives of the genus *Bacteroides* (*B.melaninogenicus*, *B.fragilis*, *B.gingivalis*). These species, according to S.F. Smola et al. (2003), are permanent inhabitants of gingival pockets in adults. No less important place in the anaerobic group is occupied by peptococci, which are most often in associations with fusobacteria and spirochaetes. Anaerobic microorganisms vegetate in the gingival sulcus, where the oxygen concentration does not exceed 0.5%. Many researchers have proved the influence of these microorganisms on the development of odontogenic inflammatory diseases of the maxillofacial region and the development of periodontal diseases. [5]

The resident oral microflora is an etiological factor in the occurrence of an infectious inflammatory process in the early postoperative period, such as after tumor removal or dental implant surgery. Through the accumulation of necrotic masses, ischaemia and hypoxia in the surrounding tissues, favorable conditions are created for even greater microbial proliferation. Yeast-like fungi, protozoa and some aerobic bacteria account for the remaining, much smaller part of microbiocenosis. The presence of pathogenic properties in representatives of oral microflora was revealed in the study of aggression enzymes in fusobacteria, *Weilonella*, microaerophilic and hemolytic streptococci, *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from oral mucosa by which the resident microflora can go beyond the ecological niche of habitation in the body and colonize in the periodontal, bone, muscle tissues. [15]

Some Gram-negative bacteria have a sharply pronounced ability to adhere, whereas Gram-positive bacteria have a much lower ability to adhere.

Microorganisms in the oral cavity always colonize materials used in dental practice.

Microorganisms in the plaque on removable dentures can provoke "acrylic" or "denture" stomatitis. The works of V.N. Tsarev (2000) proved the dependence of the organism's structural integrity, local and general reaction, expressed in the development of inflammation and allergy, on the degree of the basic materials susing. Therefore, the state of the patient's oral microecology, composition and amount of microflora are essential in selecting a constructive material. Many authors believe that the dominant cause of changes in the prosthetic field and oral mucosa caused by dentures are not the materials used in dentures but mechanical damage and violations of the biological equilibrium of the oral microflora. Wearing a removable denture leads to changes in the qualitative and quantitative composition of the oral microbiocenosis of the patient, as the zentotoxic and cytolytic effects of the monomer disturb the equilibrium of the oral microflora. A significant number of patients using removable acrylic dentures have oral secretions of *E. coli* (10 to 63%), yeast-like fungi (10-34%), pathogenic *staphylococcus aureus* (10-22%), *enterococcus* (22%), which do not usually occur in patients with intact dentition. [18,19]

N.I.Balakliets et al. (1991) showed that the composition of oral microflora depends on the preservation of teeth. Thus, in persons with intact dentition the density of microbial colonization is 4×10^6 COE/cm², with complete loss of teeth it decreases to 5×10^3 CFU. At the same time, the number of anaerobic representatives decreases sharply, up to their complete disappearance. M.S.Sarkisyan et al (2000) have shown that in case of partial tooth loss total microbial semen of oral cavity is $3,6 \times 10^3$ COE/cm², the number of staphylococci, corinebacteria, leptotrichia is high and the number of micrococci, lactobacilli are low. Complete loss of teeth is accompanied by a decrease in the index of microbial colonization of the oral cavity to $2,5 \times 10^3$ COE/cm², which does not differ in composition from that in people with intact dentition. In recent years, evidence has accumulated that bacteria play an important role in the occurrence and maintenance of pathological conditions in the oral cavity, especially when immunity is reduced. [20,17]

According to the literature, facultatively anaerobic bacteria and obligate anaerobic bacteria with unexpressed adhesive, invasive and toxic properties can acquire the ability to cause infection on their own, especially in the presence of damaged tissues when the immune status is compromised. Changes in the species and quantitative composition of the microflora of various human biotopes can occur during infectious processes of various etiologies, stress effects, and antimicrobial AND cytostatic drugs [10.]

The immunosuppressive effects of tumors and the use of cytostatic drugs lead to a decrease in cellular and humoral factors of nonspecific resistance of the body, affecting the function of individual organs and systems [12].

Such a condition contributes to a decrease in microbiological (colonization) resistance, activation of conditionally pathogenic flora, translocation of pathogenic bacteria, and the development of additional foci of endogenous and exogenous infection, which significantly aggravates the condition of the cancer patient. [16] Considering this fact, it is necessary to closely monitor cancer patients in the immediate postoperative period since most of these patients certainly have a reduced immunological status. The presence and severity of complications arising from dental oncological pathology in patients determine the problem's medico-biological and social significance.

The patient's sensitivity to the basic material of the therapeutic apparatus and the stability of the oral microbiocenosis are of great importance. These are fundamental factors that contribute to the mobilization of adaptation-compensatory mechanisms that support the organism's homeostasis. [22]

Nowadays, many research results have been accumulated that describe the features of plaque formation on direct composite restorations, restorative materials, dental ceramics, metal alloys, and polymeric materials (acrylic and polyurethane). Currently, a well-established concept of microbial adhesion to objects with different surfaces has been formed. At the first stage of plaque formation, the initial interactions between the microorganism and the substrate, i.e., hydrophobic and electrostatic interactions, are decisive. Thermodynamic studies of the attachment of *Candida* cultures to various polymeric and ceramic dental materials have suggested that hydrophobic interactions play an important role in attachment. The study of the adhesion mechanisms showed several main ways of realizing the adhesion of bacteria to the affected tissues: through chemically active molecules of the cell wall and specific tufts of bacterial cells-fimbriae and pili. The invasive properties of microorganisms are due to the production of enzymes and toxins with hemolytic, hemotoxic, necrotic, histolytic, neurotoxic or other mechanisms of action. [23]

After the placement of removable dentures, a denture biofilm forms within two weeks, including stabilizing and virulent microbial species [24].

Some species of oral microorganisms are particularly active in growing and multiplying on the surface of dentures. The denture changes color, ages over time and becomes a permanent repository for microbes [8]. It has been found that plastic is most susceptible to the damaging effects of these microorganisms.

Patients with removable dentures experience an imbalance of microflora, inhibition of indigene microflora and an increase in the excretion of pathogenic and transient microorganisms such as *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida* fungi [4] and even *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [9]. Such patients more often create conditions for the growth and excessive reproduction of normal microflora and the appearance of pathogenic forms due to impaired self-cleansing of the oral mucosa surface. [11]

Exacerbation of the toxic effect of plastic on the tissues and organs of the oral cavity due to the violation mentioned above of the biological equilibrium of the microflora contributes to the thermal insulating effect of the plastic base of the removable denture. The temperature increase under the plastic denture base leads to loosening of the mucous membrane of the denture bed, increased permeability of the vascular wall, and provokes the appearance of allergic reactions in the body. Therefore, close attention should be paid to the construction materials, quality of manufacturing and fitting of prostheses used in prosthetics of patients with a jaw defect. The data available in the literature on the choice of basal plastic in the prosthetics of patients with jaw defects refers only to patients with complete adentia. [13]

In addition, yeast-like fungi of the genus *Candida* play a special role in oral microbiocenosis. In the microflora of a healthy person, the content of these representatives is extremely low. However, many authors believe that *Candida* fungi lead to the development of denture stomatitis. Consequently, it can be assumed that the use of dentures creates conditions for the reproduction of fungi. Given that the elderly are more likely to use removable dentures, systemic factors such as diabetes mellitus, nutritional disorders, immunosuppression, xerostomia, and various medications may influence the growth of fungi. Local factors must also be considered: mechanical trauma, level of denture hygiene,

and excessive consumption of carbohydrates, which provide additional food for *Candida* fungi and bacteria. However, this is not a monotonous environment. What is unique about the oral cavity is that it is the only place in the body that contains hard, non-renewable surfaces consisting of natural tooth tissues - enamel, dentin, root cement, and various dental materials [21].

Conclusion. Thus, despite improving materials used at the present stage in orthopedic dentistry, the dysbiosis of basal materials remains unresolved. The study of the mechanisms of adhesion and colonization of individual representatives of the oral microbial flora to various types of prosthetic materials seems promising in the aspect under consideration.

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